

Croatia

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Croatia, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the Croatian higher education system comprises three types of HEIs:

- Universities and their constituents (faculties, academies of arts, university departments)
- Polytechnics
- Colleges

Universities and their constituents organise and deliver study programmes at all levels of the qualification framework. Universities most frequently make their studies available through faculties, academies, or departments. Faculties and academies are usually separate institutions of higher education (although integral parts of universities), which means that they provide study programmes and undertake scientific and professional activities in one or more scientific and professional fields, and act as legal entities. University departments, on the other hand, provide study programmes in one specific area and field, and, as a rule, they are part of universities' integrated activities. Polytechnics and colleges organise and deliver professional study programmes and perform professional activities and, if licenced, they can also perform scientific activity in specific area.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 provides a compact overview on some basic institutional characteristics along the three HEI types existing in the Croatian HE system. In total there are 40 HEIs established in Croatia, by and large quite equally distributed across the three types under consideration. In more detail, 16 Polytechnics are the most present HEIs, followed by 13 Colleges and 11 Universities. A significant share of institutions (almost 50%) is privately owned and organized, in particular the Colleges for which more than 75% are private organisations. Contrarily, Universities and Polytechnics are mostly public organisations. However, the majority of students are enrolled in public higher education institutions. Universities are the only type allowed to award PhDs. In fact, more than 90% of all Universities (10) are PhD awarding, and only one is not. Accordingly, 25% of all institutions in the Croatian HE system are PhD awarding.

¹<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/croatia/types-higher-education-institutions>

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
Polytechnic	Veleucilište	16	11	5	0
College	Visoka škola	13	3	10	0
University	sveucilište	11	9	2	10
Total		40	23	17	10

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of the evolution of the Croatian HE system over time. Figure 1 below shows that the Croatian HE system has very recent roots, which are strongly driven by the evolution and development of Croatia.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

In short, Croatia was first part of the Austrian-Hungarian empire until 1918. In 1918 Croatia became part of the Kingdom of Slovenias, Croats and Serbs, later called the Kingdom of Yugoslavia. Thereafter Croatia was part of the former Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia from 1945 to 1991. In 1991 Croatia declared its independence. In relation to this, most institutions existing in the Croatia HE system today have just been established after the Croatian declaration of independence in 1991. The University of Zagreb is the oldest Croatian University with its roots dating back to 1669, and formally established in 1874. Under the premises of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia three further Universities have been established in the 1970s. However, additional HEIs have only been founded from 1995 onwards after the Higher Education Act was enacted in 1993, introducing again a binary system of higher education in Croatia. Following this Education Act, we can observe a very steep increase in the number of foundations, with the new establishments occurring across all three HEI types. Polytechnics and Colleges have exclusively been founded after 1995, which was also done in the context of trying to position Croatia as candidate country for the European Union (ratified in 2013).

Students

Figure 2 provides an overview on the number of students enrolled, disaggregated by ISCED level across the three Croatian institution types. It is clearly illustrated that the vast majority of students are enrolled in Universities. Although they account for slightly less than one third of all institutions, they account for 82% of total students.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Total students includes ISCED 5-7.

Given that Universities are the only PhD awarding HEI type in Croatia, 100% of all PhD students are enrolled there. The share of Master students is also quite high with about 87% of all Master students being enrolled in Universities. For Bachelor students the share is 75%. Polytechnics show the second highest share of total students (about 13%), with a strong orientation towards Bachelor students. Colleges, on the other hand, having the second highest number of establishments, just enroll slightly less than 5% of all students.

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority.

As shown by Figure 3, there are no data available for colleges but only for the categories University and Polytechnic. The majority of personell (about 83%) is affiliated with universities although there is a smaller number of universities (11) than polytechnics (16) (see Table 1), i.e. universities are on average and in terms of staff much larger HEIs than polytechnics. In the Croation system, staff is distinguished between academic personnel, and research and teaching assistants; data for administrative staff are not available. The distribution between academic personnel and research and teaching assistants is quite similar between the two categories under consideration, with a slightly smaller share of acadcdemic staff in polytechnics (78%) than universities (81%).

Figure 3. Personnel (HC) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Financial resources

Figure 4 complements the results from the previous section showing the distribution of students enrolled and total academic personnel across HEI types for the year 2020. It underlines the dominating role of Universities not only for students enrolled (82%), but also in terms of academic personnel where the share of Universities accounting for about 88% is even higher than for students enrolled, i.e. Universities show the highest staff-to-student ratio as compared to the other two HEI types. For Polytechnics, the share of total academic personnel (about 8%) is clearly below the share of students enrolled (about 13%). For Colleges, we find a similar pattern, with a 5% share of total students enrolled but just a 4% share of total academic personnel.

Figure 4. Resources, academic personnel and total students enrolled by type of HEI, 2020

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students, data show a more or less steady pattern, with the total number of enrolled students staying at around 150,000 between 2011 to 2020 (see Figure 5). Also the share between the three categories is more or less stable. Relating this to the relatively high number of new establishments of HEIs between 2011 and 2020 (see also Figure 1), it is somewhat surprising that the number of students has not increased, but even slightly decreased between 2013 and 2015 and after 2017. This may be related to an increasing number of students studying abroad, in particular after the ratification of Croatia becoming a full member of the European Union in 2013.

Figure 5. Share of students enrolled by type of HEI, 2011-2020

As shown by Figure 6, there are – similar to the share and total number of students enrolled – very minor changes over time, both in total academic personnel as well as in the share between the categories. The most notable point here is a slight increase in total academic personnel from 2017 to 2019, while numbers of students enrolled slightly decrease since 2017. One reason for this could be that the Croatian HE system is trying to improve the student-teacher ratio, or that some HEIs try to address their research mission more prominently by shifting resources from teaching to research.

Figure 6. Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2011-2020

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